

Comparative Modeling of a Solar Thermal System: Physics-Based and Data-Driven Approaches

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Abstract—Accurate modeling of solar thermal systems is essential for optimizing performance, reducing maintenance costs, and supporting intelligent monitoring and control. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of a real-world solar thermal installation by comparing physics-based transient modeling in TRNSYS with data-driven models derived from high-resolution IoT measurements. The different models aim to reproduce the dynamic behavior of the solar collector, storage tank, and heat exchanger using environmental inputs, enabling a comparative assessment of their respective strengths and limitations. The TRNSYS model performance is validated against experimental data, and a comparative analysis is conducted with two data-driven models, Polynomial Regression (PR) and Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (ARX), highlighting the trade-offs between physics-based interpretability and data-driven modeling accuracy. The study further explores the potential for integrating models into embedded PLCs to enable real-time performance prediction, anomaly detection, and predictive maintenance, laying the foundation for intelligent monitoring and control of solar thermal systems. The results demonstrate that combining physics-based and data-driven modeling provides a powerful framework for both research and practical applications in renewable energy system optimization.

Keywords—Data-Driven Models, Performance Evaluation, Physics-Based Modeling, Solar Thermal System

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background And Motivation

Solar thermal systems play a vital role in reducing fossil fuel consumption for domestic hot water production, space heating, and industrial processes. The design and evaluation of these systems increasingly rely on modeling and simulation tools capable of capturing transient environmental effects, system dynamics, and control strategies [1]. A variety of software environments have been developed to address these needs. For large-scale feasibility studies and system optimization, Polysun [2] is widely adopted in engineering practice due to its user-friendly interfaces and extensive component databases. For building-integrated analyses, EnergyPlus [3] enables coupling with Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) loads, making it suitable for architectural and building energy studies.

When a higher level of physical detail is required, Matlab/Simulink [4], [5] or Modelica/Dymola [6], and

Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) tools such as ANSYS Fluent [7] and COMSOL Multiphysics [8] are preferred. These platforms allow fine-resolution modeling of collectors, heat exchangers, and stratified tanks, particularly in component-level design and optimization.

Despite these capabilities, system-level studies that require transient performance evaluation and flexible component coupling are most effectively conducted using TRNSYS (Transient System Simulation Tool) [9], [10]. TRNSYS is widely recognized in research and industry for its modular architecture, extensive libraries, and ability to incorporate custom models and control algorithms. Its component-based structure enables seamless assembly of collectors, storage units, auxiliary heaters, and control devices, making it particularly suited for dynamic simulation of solar thermal systems. Furthermore, TRNSYS supports interoperability with other environments such as MATLAB or Python [11], enhancing its applicability for hybrid modeling, data-driven calibration, and advanced control strategies. As a result, TRNSYS has become one of the most used platforms for modeling and performance analysis of thermal systems, including residential and industrial heat supply.

The motivation of this work arises from the need to validate simulation models with real measured data. In this study, a real-world, IoT-based experimental solar thermal installation located in Granges, Switzerland, is used as the testbed [12]. By integrating experimental data into the modeling workflow, the study aims not only to assess the accuracy of TRNSYS in reproducing real system behavior but also to demonstrate how simulation models can be refined through data-driven calibration. Furthermore, the TRNSYS model is compared with alternative data-driven machine learning models [13], [14], [15] developed on the same experimental setup, providing a comprehensive benchmark that highlights the relative strengths and limitations of physics-based simulation versus purely data-driven approaches. This comparison allows for a deeper understanding of the trade-offs between model interpretability, predictive accuracy, and applicability in the context of solar thermal system modeling.

B. Contribution of This Study

This study provides several significant contributions to the modeling and performance analysis of solar thermal systems. First, it develops a detailed and experimentally validated

TRNSYS model of a real flat-plate solar thermal installation equipped with IoT-based monitoring technologies. The model incorporates high-resolution environmental and operational data, as well as computationally derived inputs such as incidence angle and irradiance decomposition obtained through pvlb, thereby improving the representation of dynamic boundary conditions. Second, this work demonstrates a systematic methodology for refining the TRNSYS model through rigorous testing and analysis, in which experimental measurements are compared with TRNSYS simulated variables for model validation and to ensure accurate representation of the system's actual operating behavior. Third, a comparative evaluation is conducted between TRNSYS and two data-driven machine learning models, Polynomial Regression (PR) and Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (ARX) trained on a selected dataset. This benchmarking highlights the relative advantages and limitations of physics-based and data-driven modeling strategies in terms of accuracy, reliability, and applicability under varying operating conditions. Finally, the study provides a framework that can be applied to future research on hybrid simulation approaches, predictive maintenance, and advanced control strategies for solar thermal systems.

C. Organization of This Paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a detailed description of the experimental solar thermal installation, including its thermal and hydraulic layout, sensors network, and IoT-based data acquisition architecture. Section III introduces the TRNSYS modeling framework, outlines the selected components, and explains how experimental and computationally derived inputs are integrated into the simulation workflow. Section IV reports the simulation results, comparing TRNSYS outputs with measured data and with two data-driven machine learning models to evaluate accuracy and predictive performance. Section V concludes the paper by summarizing the key outcomes, discussing the strengths and limitations of each modeling approach, and identifying promising directions for future research.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The experimental solar thermal system, illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of a vertical flat-plate solar thermal panel equipped with a glass cover and a serpentine heat exchanger tube through which water circulates to enhance heat transfer efficiency. The system includes a 150-liter insulated storage tank that accumulates the harvested thermal energy, while a 12-liter expansion vessel ensures stable operating pressure. Fluid circulation is managed by a pump regulated by a dedicated control unit, which optimizes operation according to temperature conditions. To emulate domestic hot water demand, an auxiliary cooling unit with an integrated heat exchanger is also incorporated into the setup.

The installation is implemented in Granges, Valais, Switzerland (46.264765° N, 7.465038° E). The main characteristics of the flat-plate solar thermal panel and storage tank are summarized in Tables I and II, respectively. Under standard test conditions, the flat-plate solar thermal panel delivers a nominal thermal power of 1155 W, corresponding to the rated capacity of the system.

Fig. 1. Key components of the solar thermal installation in Granges, Switzerland.

TABLE I. KEY PARAMETERS OF THE SOLAR THERMAL PANEL

Parameter	Value
Gross area	2.53 m ²
Aperture/absorber area	2.33 m ²
Optical efficiency (η_0 , aperture)	81.7 %
Heat loss coefficients	$a_1 = 4.2 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$, $a_2 = 0.013 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\text{K}^{-2}$
Maximum operating pressure	10 bar

TABLE II. KEY PARAMETERS OF THE STORAGE TANK

Parameter	Value
Nominal volume	150 L (usable 148 L)
Heat exchanger surface	0.6 m ²
Maximum working pressure	Tank: 10 bar (90 °C), HX: 12 bar (110 °C)
Insulation type	Hard polyurethane foam
Internal protection	Polywarm® coating with magnesium anode

To monitor and control the experimental platform, an IoT-based monitoring and control System [12] is implemented, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The system integrates multiple field sensors, including PT100 probes used to measure ambient temperature (T_{amb}), inlet and outlet temperatures of the solar thermal panel (T_{in} , T_{out}) and the heat exchanger (T_{inHE} , T_{outHE}) as well as the storage tank temperature (T_{tank}). Two flow meters measure the water circulation through the serpentine tube of the solar thermal panel (q_{STC}) as well as the flow through the external heat exchanger (q_{HE}) employed to emulate domestic hot water consumption. Additionally, two pyranometers are used to measure solar irradiance: one installed in the same plane as the panel to accurately quantify the incident radiation, and another mounted horizontally to measure global irradiance. The performance of the STC system can be evaluated based on its thermal output power, which is calculated using fundamental principles and governed by the nonlinear interaction between the flow rate and the temperature difference across the solar thermal concentrator. The thermal power is given by the following expression, where C_f is the heat capacity of the fluid:

$$P_{TH}(t) = q_{STC} C_f (T_{out}(t) - T_{in}(t)) \quad (1)$$

All the variables are sampled at 30-second intervals by a Beckhoff Programmable Logic Controller (PLC), which performs high-frequency data acquisition, supervisory control, and actuator management, including real-time pump regulation. The PLC communicates with I/O modules to collect sensors data and is connected via Ethernet to HOOE Gateways, which enable secure remote access and cloud communication. Data streams are processed by Node-RED, ensuring structured transfer to an

InfluxDB time-series database hosted on Microsoft Azure, supporting scalable and secure long-term storage. Visualization and analysis are facilitated through Grafana, which provides an interactive web-based platform for real-time monitoring, historical trend analysis, and comprehensive performance evaluation.

Fig. 2. The IoT-based monitoring and control system architecture for the experimental solar thermal installation.

Fig. 3 provides a user-friendly environment through a Human Machine Interface (HMI), enabling intuitive real-time monitoring and interaction with the system. It illustrates the overall hydraulic and thermal configuration, including the flat-plate solar panel, the storage tank equipped with an internal heat exchanger, circulation pumps, and a secondary heat exchanger with a fan used to emulate domestic hot water demand. This interface supports effective interaction with the system, providing clear visualization of measurements and control states to facilitate accurate assessment and efficient operation of the experimental platform.

Fig. 3. The HMI interface for real-time monitoring of the solar thermal installation.

III. TRNSYS FOR SOLAR THERMAL SYSTEMS SIMULATION

TRNSYS (Transient System Simulation Tool) is one of the most widely used simulation environments for modeling and analyzing thermal systems. Its popularity stems from its modular architecture, which allows researchers and engineers to assemble complex energy systems using configurable physical models. TRNSYS has been extensively applied in the design, optimization, and performance evaluation of solar water heating systems due to its flexibility, transient simulation capabilities, and validated component models. This makes TRNSYS particularly suitable for accurately predicting thermal behavior under variable operating and climate conditions.

At the core of TRNSYS lies a library of predefined components, referred to as TYPES, which represent real physical elements such as solar collectors, storage tanks, heat exchangers, pumps, sensors, and controllers. These components rely on mathematical models built primarily in

Fortran, a language historically used in scientific computing for its numerical stability and performance. Newer or user-defined models may be developed in C or C++. Each TYPE is governed by explicit physical equations based on algebraic relationships and differential formulations, enabling dynamic representation of thermally driven processes such as heat transfer, stratification, or fluid circulation. This modular structure also facilitates the integration of external tools such as MATLAB or Python, enhancing analytical capabilities, control design, and data-driven parameter calibration.

Unlike conventional programming-based simulation tools, TRNSYS provides a low-code graphical workflow. Users create systems by selecting, placing, and connecting TYPES in the Simulation Studio environment. During execution, TRNSYS automatically generates a deck file that stores model structure, component parameters, and state variables. When a simulation is launched, the TRNSYS kernel reads this file, checks its validity, verifies links to external data, and iteratively computes system behavior. The kernel uses a successive substitution algorithm, whereby each component is evaluated multiple times at every timestep until convergence is achieved within a predefined tolerance. If convergence is not reached within the maximum number of iterations, TRNSYS proceeds with a warning to highlight that simulation reliability depends strongly on model calibration and consistent input data.

In the present study, TRNSYS is employed to model the experimental solar thermal installation described in section II. As seen in Fig. 4, the TRNSYS model of the solar thermal system is structured around five fully coupled components that represent the solar collector panel, the thermal storage tank, the fan-assisted heat exchanger, and the external data inputs.

Fig. 4. The TRNSYS architecture of the solar thermal system including solar collector panel, storage tank, heat exchanger, and external data inputs.

All climatic inputs and boundary-condition data required for the solar radiation calculations are provided by TYPE 9c, which serves as the external data reader. This component imports the measured ambient temperature T_{amb} and the global horizontal irradiance from the experimental data set. As Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) and Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI) are not measured on site, they are reconstructed numerically using the Python library “pvlib”. More specifically, its “irradiance.erbs” function is applied to decompose the measured global irradiance into its direct and diffuse components. These resulting climatic variables are then supplied to the radiation processor TYPE 16k.

TYPE 16k serves as a radiation preprocessing interface between the external climatic data and the solar collector model (TYPE 1b). Using the collector geometry and orientation, it projects the solar irradiance onto the tilted surface and

computes the effective incident radiation θ_{INC} by accounting for solar position and radiation geometry. This ensures that the collector model receives physically consistent and correctly oriented solar radiation inputs.

TYPE 1b represents the flat-plate solar thermal collector, which converts incident solar radiation into useful thermal energy transferred to the circulating fluid. Its performance depends on the effective irradiance on the collector panel, the fluid inlet temperature, and ambient conditions. The collector receives the processed solar radiation S_f and the incidence angle θ_{INC} from the radiation processor, ensuring physically consistent radiation inputs. TYPE 1b outputs the outlet fluid temperature T_{out} , which is supplied to the thermal storage.

Thermal storage is modeled by TYPE 156, a dynamic boiler model that accounts for stratification, thermal losses, and variable mass flow rates. It updates the internal temperature distribution based on heat supplied by the solar collector and heat extracted through the load-side heat exchanger. The cooler return flow from the tank is recirculated to the collector, closing the hydraulic loop and influencing collector efficiency.

Heat extraction and demand dynamics are represented by TYPE 137, which models a fan-assisted heat exchanger. In this component, hot water from the storage tank exchanges heat with a forced air stream, emulating space-heating or domestic hot-water demand. Fan operation and heat rejection are governed by external control signals, imposing a realistic and time-dependent thermal load on the system.

The parameterization of the TRNSYS components is based on manufacturer datasheets, measured system characteristics, and iterative calibration against experimental data. Key parameters influencing system performance include the collector optical efficiency and heat loss coefficients, the stratification node configuration and thermal loss coefficients of the storage tank, and the heat transfer coefficients in the fan-assisted heat exchanger. A preliminary sensitivity analysis is conducted by varying these parameters within physically realistic ranges to evaluate their influence on outlet temperature and delivered thermal power.

IV. RESULTS

The results presented in this section evaluate the performance of the TRNSYS model of the solar thermal installation and compare it with two data-driven machine learning models developed on the same experimental setup. The typical architecture of the system as implemented in TRNSYS Simulation Studio is illustrated in Fig. 5, which highlights the main components, solar thermal panel, storage tank, heat exchanger network, hydraulic circuit along with their interconnections. This simulation architecture closely reflects the physical configuration of the experimental installation, ensuring consistency between the numerical model and real operating conditions.

To assess the modeling accuracy, simulated outputs are compared with experimental measurements for a representative test day (June 17, 2025). This spring day is characterized by global solar irradiance varying from approximately 400 W/m^2 at 9:00 a.m. to about 900 W/m^2 around midday.

Fig. 5. Architecture of the solar thermal system in TRNSYS Simulation Studio.

Figures 6 to 9 present the time-series comparison between measured and simulated values for four key variables sampled at 30-second intervals: the inlet and outlet temperatures of the solar collector loop (T_{in} , T_{out}), the storage tank temperature (T_{tank}), and the delivered thermal power (P_{TH}) to the load.

The overall performance of the TRNSYS model is quantified using the coefficient of determination R^2 . This quantitative evaluation provides a clear and objective basis for assessing model accuracy across the four analyzed variables. High R^2 values indicate that the simulation captures a large portion of the experimental variability, confirming the relevance of the TRNSYS architecture and parameterization strategies used in the study.

Fig. 6. Simulated vs. measured values for inlet temperature ($R^2 = 0.988$).

Fig. 7. Simulated vs. measured values for outlet temperature ($R^2 = 0.955$).

Fig. 8. Simulated vs. measured values for tank temperature ($R^2 = 0.982$).

Fig. 9. Simulated vs. measured values for delivered thermal power ($R^2=0.950$).

To further contextualize the modeling performance of TRNSYS, the same testing day is modeled using two data-driven approaches, PR and ARX [13], [14], [15]. These models are trained on an experimental dataset of four days in June 2025, with all variables sampled at 30-second intervals and filtered using a 5-point moving average and are evaluated under identical conditions to ensure a fair comparison. The dataset corresponds to a limited period and mainly reflects late-spring conditions. Therefore, the reported results demonstrate short-term predictive capability under similar climatic conditions. Long-term generalization under seasonal variability and extreme weather remains to be investigated using extended datasets.

A PR model is a static modeling approach that expresses the output of a system, in our case, the thermal power P_{TH} as a nonlinear function of the input variables, namely solar irradiance S_I and ambient temperature T_{amb} , represented through polynomial terms. The nonlinearity arises from the inclusion of higher-order powers of the inputs, which allows the model to capture nonlinear input-output relationships. However, the model is static, since the output at time t depends only on the current values of the inputs and does not involve past inputs or past outputs. After evaluating various polynomial orders, we found that a second order polynomial offers the best balance between accuracy and complexity, since the higher order models had larger errors. The second-order PR model can be represented by the following equation:

$$P_{TH}(t) = a_0 + a_1 S_I(t) + a_2 T_{amb}(t) + a_3 S_I^2(t) + a_4 T_{amb}^2(t) + a_5 S_I(t) T_{amb}(t) \quad (2)$$

where a_0, \dots, a_5 are determined by minimizing the least-squares error between the observed and predicted values. The calculated PR model coefficients are listed in Table III.

TABLE III. COEFFICIENTS OF THE PR MODEL

Coefficients	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5
Values	0.310	0.617	-0.874	0.539	0.696	-0.609

ARX is a dynamic modeling technique that predicts the system's behavior by incorporating both its past inputs and output. The structure of the ARX is given by:

$$A(q) P_{TH}(t) = B_1(q) S_I(t) + B_2(q) T_{amb}(t) + e(t) \quad (3)$$

where q is the delay operator. Specifically:

$$A(q) = 1 + a_1 q^{-1} + a_2 q^{-2} + \dots + a_{n_a} q^{-n_a} \quad (4)$$

$$B_1(q) = b_{11} q^{-1} + b_{12} q^{-2} + \dots + b_{1n_b} q^{-n_{b1}+1} \quad (5)$$

$$B_2(q) = b_{21} q^{-1} + b_{22} q^{-2} + \dots + b_{2n_b} q^{-n_{b2}+1} \quad (6)$$

Here, n_{b1} and n_{b2} represent the time delays associated with the inputs $S_I(t)$ and $T_{amb}(t)$, respectively, which determine the system's zeros. Similarly, n_a denotes the order of the autoregressive terms, governing the system's poles, while $e(t)$ represents the noise introduced by system disturbances. Through a systematic analysis, it was concluded that $n_a = 7$ and $n_{b1} = n_{b2} = 4$ yield the minimum error for the ARX structure. The calculated ARX model coefficients are listed in Table IV.

TABLE IV. COEFFICIENTS OF THE ARX MODEL

Coefficients	Values
A	[-1.8814, 0.8024, 0.0853, 0.0191, 0.5029, -0.9093, 0.3831]
B_1	[0.0084, -0.0107, 0.00031921, 0.0041]
B_2	[0.3554, 0.6332, -1.6509, 0.6114]

Fig. 10 illustrates the modeling performance of the three approaches for the delivered thermal power, showing the extent to which each model can reproduce the system's real dynamics.

Fig. 10. Simulated vs. measured values for delivered thermal power using TRNSYS, PR and ARX modeling, for a representative test day (June 17, 2025).

Table V reports the corresponding R^2 and RMSE values obtained with the TRNSYS, PR, and ARX models, highlighting the fundamental differences between physics-based and data-driven modeling approaches.

TABLE V. MODEL PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF TRNSYS, PR AND ARX MODELING

Model	R^2	RMSE (W)
PR	0.80	48.724
ARX	0.91	34.786
TRNSYS	0.95	30.071

TRNSYS, as a detailed physics-based simulation tool, explicitly represents the underlying physical and thermodynamic processes of the system, resulting in high accuracy, strong consistency, and excellent robustness over a wide range of operating conditions.

In contrast, the performance of data-driven models such as PR and ARX is highly dependent on the quality and representativeness of the available data. PR, as a static nonlinear model, offers simplicity and low computational cost; however, it lacks the capability to represent system dynamics and therefore fails to capture the inherently dynamic behavior of the system. Moreover, since the system dynamics are predominantly linear, the introduction of nonlinear polynomial terms in the PR model does not provide additional modeling benefits and may even degrade overall performance. As a result, PR shows limited accuracy outside the calibration domain.

ARX modeling, by explicitly incorporating system dynamics through past inputs and outputs, is better aligned with the intrinsic physical characteristics of the system. Its satisfactory performance indicates that the dominant dynamics are both linear and time-dependent, making ARX a particularly well-suited modeling choice for our solar thermal system. Compared to PR, the ARX model more effectively captures short-term temporal behavior without introducing unnecessary nonlinear complexity. Although ARX may exhibit reduced robustness when extrapolated to unseen operating conditions, its balance between simplicity and dynamic fidelity explains its superior performance relative to PR.

More advanced machine learning techniques such as neural networks could provide additional benchmarking. However, given the limited dataset size, structured models such as PR and ARX were selected to avoid overfitting and preserve interpretability.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The TRNSYS-based analysis demonstrates the capability of physics-based modeling to accurately reproduce the dynamic behavior of the solar collector, storage tank, and heat exchanger under realistic operating conditions. The close agreement between simulations, experimental measurements, and data-driven models confirms the robustness and interpretability of the physics-based approach, while highlighting the complementary value of data-driven techniques for short-term prediction.

To further strengthen the study, future work will extend the evaluation to multi-season datasets, including winter conditions, prolonged cloudy periods, and extreme summer temperatures, to assess long-term generalization. The benchmarking framework will also be expanded to incorporate advanced machine learning and hybrid physics-informed models when larger datasets become available.

Another important perspective is the real-time implementation of a reduced-order TRNSYS model on the embedded PLC. Such integration would enable continuous performance monitoring, anomaly detection, and predictive maintenance. Ultimately, combining physics-based simulation with data-driven algorithms offers a promising pathway toward reliable digital-twin frameworks for solar thermal systems, supporting real-time monitoring, optimization, and operational reliability.

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